

**A STUDY OF THE EFFECTS
OF IMPERFECTIONS AND LAY-UP
ANTISYMMETRY ON THE INITIAL
FLEXURAL FAILURE RESPONSE
OF CROSS-PLY STRIPS**

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A nonlinear elastic solution of the large deflection laminated strip equations is obtained with the aid of the Dynamic Relaxation (DR) method and combined with the Tsai-Hill failure criterion to facilitate an initial failure study of CFRP and GFRP strips. The study is largely devoted to quantifying the effects of lay-up antisymmetry and initial imperfection amplitude on the initial failure response. Numerical results for the initial failure loads and the associated additional strip centre-line deflections are presented in dimensionless graphical form to facilitate their widest application.

INTRODUCTION

A considerable proportion of the current research effort in the field of composite materials is directed towards developing an understanding of, and an ability to predict, the complete load - deformation response of laminated structural elements, eg. plates and shells. This type of research is a necessary prerequisite to the formulation of rational and economic structural design procedures. At the present time progress towards this ultimate goal is slow, particularly because of the complex nature of failure in these materials. In laminated composites failure may initiate in one of several modes, eg. fibre fracture, delamination etc., and as failure progresses mode interaction may arise. It is not surprising, therefore, that simple failure criteria are unable to model progressive failure in a generally satisfactory manner. More refined failure criteria require extensive experimentation for their complete definition and this represents a considerable handicap to their practical application, particularly as a complete set of experiments is required for each composite material system.

Unfortunately, commercial pressures are such that designers cannot await the final resolution of the research problems associated with composite materials failure, as outlined above, before making use of materials such as GFRP (Glass Fibre Reinforced Plastic) and CFRP (Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic) in their present and future designs. Consequently, for the time being, they must employ less sophisticated and more conservative design procedures. A widespread procedure is to base the design strength on the initial or first-ply failure, i.e. the design strength is arrived at via the combination of a linear or nonlinear elastic analysis and a suitably simple failure criterion, eg. the maximum strain criterion. The linear elastic form of this procedure is well developed for in-plane load configurations /1 & 2/, which commonly arise in aeronautical structural applications.

GFRP and CFRP materials are being used in an increasingly wide variety of non-aeronautical structural applications and it is to be anticipated that sometimes they will be subjected to out-of-plane (flexurally) dominant rather than in-plane dominant load configurations. It appears that only a few studies of the design strength of laminated structural elements based on the first-ply or initial failure in flexure have been reported /3 - 6/ - despite their potential usefulness to designers - and that none of these have employed nonlinear elastic analyses.

It is recognised that real structures are seldom, if ever, free from imperfections of one kind or another, which arise during the fabrication process. Amongst the many possible types of defect, the presence of initial out-of-plane deformations may usually be relied upon, particularly in laminated composites. Thus, it is important for the designer to have some guidance on the effect of initial imperfections on the strength of the laminate. Furthermore, it is known that in laminated structures lay-up antisymmetry may have the effect of considerably reducing the flexural stiffness and, therefore, the designer requires to know whether a commensurate reduction in the flexural strength may be expected. As a first step towards providing quantitative guidance on the effect of these two phenomena on the initial failure response, the relatively simple, but practical, problem of a uniformly loaded, antisymmetric cross-ply laminated strip with a single half-wave imperfection has been selected for study. Nonlinear elastic solutions to the strip equilibrium equations are obtained by means of an interlacing finite-difference implementation of the Dynamic Relaxation (DR) method /7/. A simple iterative procedure is then used to ensure compliance of the nonlinear elastic solution with a simple failure criterion (Tsai-Hill criterion) and thereby allow the initial failure response to be determined.

The present study considers strips with opposite edges either simply supported or clamped. Initial failure loads and strip centre-line deflections (additional) are evaluated and presented non-dimensionally for a range of initial imperfection amplitudes and for the upper and lower limits on the number of constituent laminae.

STRIP AND LAMINA PROPERTIES

Fig. 1(a) shows the strip geometry and the positive Cartesian co-ordinate ref-

Fig. 1(a) Strip geometry and positive co-ordinate system.

Fig. 1(b) Details of the cross-ply lay-up.

erence system. The strips are layed-up from an even number of equal thickness, unidirectional laminae such that the lamina fibre directions coincide alternately with the x and y co-ordinate directions (see Fig. 1(b)), i.e. the stacking sequence is antisymmetric.

Two types of unidirectional composite material systems are considered, viz. GFRP and CFRP. The elastic constants and failure strengths of these composite materials may vary according to the particular fibre and resin matrix types selected. However, for computational purposes, typical rather than specific values of these constants have been used. These values are given in Table 1.

Material	$E_L E_T^{-1}$	$G_{LT} E_T^{-1}$	ν_{LT}	$s_L s_T^{-1}$	$s_T c s_T^{-1}$	$s_{LT} s_T^{-1}$
GFRP	3.00	0.48	0.25	37.50	4.00	1.50
CFRP	9.40	0.36	0.30	17.85	2.64	1.43

Table 1 Stiffness and strength ratios for GFRP and CFRP unidirectional laminae.

Because of the simple type of lay-up adopted for this study, explicit formulae /8/ may be used for the calculation of the strip stiffnesses. They are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{11} &= \lambda h \alpha (M + \alpha^{-1}) (1 + M)^{-1} \\
 A_{12} &= \lambda h \alpha \nu_{LT} \\
 B_{11} &= \lambda h^2 \alpha M (\alpha^{-1} - 1) (1 + M)^{-2} N_L^{-1} \\
 D_{11} &= \lambda h^3 \alpha \{ (\alpha^{-1} - 1) R + 1 \} / 12 \\
 D_{12} &= \lambda h^3 \alpha \nu_{LT} / 12
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

in which

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda &= E_T (1 - \nu_{LT} \nu_{TL})^{-1} \\
 \alpha &= E_L E_T^{-1} \\
 M &= (\sum t_i) (\sum t_j) \quad (i = \text{odd}, j = \text{even}) \\
 R &= (1 + M)^{-1} + 8M(M - 1) (1 + M)^{-3} N_L^{-2}
 \end{aligned}$$

The remaining strip property of importance is the initial imperfection. Again a representative, rather than an actual, strip imperfection has been adopted for computational purposes, though, of course, real or other representative types of imperfection could equally well have been adopted. Thus, a single half-wave initial imperfection of the following form has been assumed:

$$w^0 = \pm w_0 \sin(\pi x/a) \tag{2}$$

The positive and negative signs in Eq. (2) apply when the lateral pressure is respectively positive and negative, i.e. it is assumed that the initial imperfection is always "sympathetic" to the lateral pressure and snap buckling may not arise.

INITIAL FLEXURAL FAILURE ANALYSIS

An initial flexural failure analysis, be it flexural or otherwise, reduces essentially to the search for an elastic stress state, i.e. an elastic solution of the equilibrium equations, which neither satisfies nor violates an appropriate failure criterion except at one point (possibly more points when geometric and loading symmetry conditions exist) where the criterion is just satisfied. Thus the constituent parts of the initial failure analysis are: the elastic governing equations (equilibrium, compatibility etc.) and the failure criterion. These components are considered in greater detail below:

Strip Equilibrium Equations

Under conditions of cylindrical bending (conditions which are assumed to apply in the present study) the strip equilibrium may be described in terms of the following two coupled, ordinary differential equations:

$$N_x^* = 0$$

$$M_x^* + N_x^* w^{**} + q = 0$$
(3)

The first of Eq. (3) implies that N_x is constant throughout the strip, but this feature cannot be utilised readily to x advantage because of the geometric nonlinearity present in the compatibility equations (see Eq. (4) below).

Nonlinear Compatibility Equations

The nonlinear strip compatibility equations may be expressed as follows:

$$\epsilon_x = u^* + \frac{1}{2} w_1^{*2} + w^0 \cdot w_1^*$$

$$\kappa_x = -w_1^{**}$$
(4)

It should be appreciated that only the strains contain nonlinear terms; the curvatures are linear functions of the displacements and are identical with the expressions used in small deflection theory.

Coupled Constitutive Equations

Laminated strips may or may not exhibit coupling between in-plane and out-of-plane quantities depending on the type of lay-up adopted. In the present study, antisymmetric cross-ply lay-ups are considered and these exhibit what is commonly termed "extensional - flexural" coupling. Thus, the constitutive equations take the following form:

$$N_x = A_{11} \epsilon_x + B_{11} \kappa_x$$

$$M_x = B_{11} \epsilon_x + D_{11} \kappa_x$$
(5)

Boundary Conditions

Only two types of symmetric flexural boundary conditions are considered, viz. simply supported and clamped. In each case full in-plane restraint is assumed. Hence, the boundary conditions may be expressed in terms of the following restrictions on the problem variables along the strip edges ($x = 0, a$):

$$u = w = M_x = 0$$

or $u = w = w^* = 0$

(6)

Tsai-Hill Failure Criterion

Of the simpler criteria that may be used to predict the failure of fibre reinforced materials, the Tsai-Hill criterion has been shown to be amongst the more accurate /9/, particularly for in-plane loading states in GFRP materials. For this reason, it has been adopted for the present analysis.

The stress state within a thin laminated strip is essentially two-dimensional, so that the two-dimensional form of the failure criterion is appropriate. This may be expressed as:

$$(s_1^2 - s_1 s_2) s_L^{-2} + \eta^{-2} s_2^2 s_T^{-2} + s_{12}^2 s_{LT}^{-2} = 1$$
(7)

Because of the nature of the strip lay-up, s_{12} is zero in all of the laminae and hence Eq. (7) reduces to:

$$\bar{\delta}^2 s_1 (s_1 - s_2) + \bar{\eta}^2 s_2^2 = s_{T_t}^2 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{in which } \bar{\delta} = \delta^{-1}$$

$$\bar{\eta} = \eta^{-1}$$

$$\delta = s_L s_{T_t}^{-1}$$

$$\text{and } \eta = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{when } s_2 \text{ is tensile.} \\ s_{T_c} s_{T_t}^{-1} & \text{when } s_2 \text{ is compressive.} \end{cases}$$

Evaluation of the Initial Failure Loads and Associated Deflections

A starting value for the applied lateral pressure is selected (guessed or rationally chosen). Eqs. (3) - (6) are then solved for this value of the lateral pressure, i.e. the nonlinear elastic solution is obtained using the DR method and this solution is used to establish the equilibrium stress field within the strip. Lamina stresses may then be determined using simple transformation relationships /8/. It is then a simple matter to establish whether lamina failure has occurred at any point within the strip - the lamina stresses are simply substituted into Eq. (8) and violation or otherwise of the failure criterion is immediately apparent. In general, the initial failure condition, as defined at the beginning of this section of the paper, will not be met for the starting value of the lateral pressure. Hence, the pressure is adjusted according to whether the initial failure has been exceeded/not exceeded and the problem is then re-analysed. This trial and error procedure is continued until the initial failure condition is satisfied to the desired degree of accuracy. The load for which the last analysis was performed is then taken as the initial failure load. Other quantities of interest, eg. the associated strip centre-line deflection etc., have been calculated during the final iterative solution of Eqs. (3) - (6) and are, therefore, readily available.

DR Solution Procedure

The DR iterative method is well suited to nonlinear structural analysis and, for this reason, has been chosen for the solution of Eqs. (3) - (6). Full details of the application of the method to large deflection structural analyses are not given here, but, instead, may be consulted elsewhere /10/. For the large deflection strip analyses of this paper an interlacing finite-difference formulation has been adopted and rationally determined fictitious densities have been employed. Both of these features tend to improve the solution accuracy and the stability of the iterations (see /11/ for further details of these features in the context of strip analyses). Advantage was taken of both loading and geometric symmetry, so that the DR procedure was applied only to one half of the strip, thereby considerably reducing the computational effort.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As designers are primarily interested in assessing how well their structures meet the imposed strength and serviceability criteria, the numerical output of this study is restricted to the two most relevant quantities, i.e. the initial failure loads and the associated additional strip centre-line deflections.

Initial failure loads plotted against the magnitude of the initial imperfection are shown in Figs. 2 and 3 for CFRP and GFRP strips respectively. Fig. 2(a), which shows the results obtained for simply supported CFRP strips, indicates that the failure loads increase almost linearly as the imperfection amplitude increases. The rate of increase of the failure load is only moderate for two-layer strips, in which "extensional - flexural" coupling is most pronounced; but is significantly greater

Fig. 2(a) Initial failure load versus imperfection amplitude for a simply supported CFRP strip.

Fig. 2(b) Initial failure load versus imperfection amplitude for a clamped CFRP strip.

Fig. 3(a) Initial failure load versus imperfection amplitude for a simply supported GFRP strip.

in the uncoupled strips (compare the slopes of the full and broken line curves). The figure also indicates that the magnitude of the initial failure load depends on the direction of the applied loading. Thus, simply supported CFRP strips are significantly stronger when the loading is in the negative z-direction than when it is in the positive direction. Yet another feature of Fig. 2(a) is the divergence of the two-layer and uncoupled results with increasing imperfection amplitude. The remaining feature of note concerning Fig. 2(a) is that the uncoupled initial failure loads always exceed the corresponding two-layer values regardless of the size of the initial imperfection and the direction of loading.

Initial failure loads for clamped CFRP strips are presented in Fig. 2(b). It is apparent that the initial failure load - imperfection amplitude relationship is mildly nonlinear, rather than linear, under clamped edge conditions. Furthermore, the initial failure loads increase with increasing imperfection amplitude and the rate of increase is broadly similar for both two-layer and uncoupled strips. Under clamped edge conditions the CFRP strips also exhibit direction dependent initial failure loads, but, in contrast to simply supported strips, higher strengths arise when the load is applied in the positive z-direction. Fig. 2(b) also suggests that the difference between the uncoupled and two-layer initial failure loads does not increase significantly as the imperfection amplitude increases (see the curves labelled (b)). Indeed, there is evidence to the contrary, for the curves labelled (a) tend to coalesce when the imperfection amplitude is large. This feature may be accounted for by the fact that failure initiates in a fundamentally different manner in the two-layer strip to that in the uncoupled strip when the load is applied in the positive z-direction - the two-layer strips fail at/near the strip centre and the uncoupled strips fail at the supports. These failure mode differences between clamped uncoupled and clamped two-layer strips also explain why the uncoupled initial failure loads do not lie wholly above the two-layer failure loads, as is the case with simply supported strips.

The initial failure load - imperfection amplitude plots for simply supported and clamped GFRP strips are presented in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) respectively. In most

Fig. 3(b) Initial failure load versus imperfection amplitude for a clamped CFRP strip.

respects, they are broadly similar to the corresponding results for CFRP strips and, therefore, will not be discussed further here.

In the above discussion, certain features of the failure load - imperfection amplitude plots have been attributed to differences in the failure mode or, more precisely, the point(s) at which failure initiated. A closer examination of the results shows that failure always initiates at the strip surface. Furthermore, in flat strips the point(s) of failure may be either at the supports, or at the strip centre, depending on whether: coupling is present or absent, the loading direction is positive or negative, and the strip edges are clamped or simply supported. In the case of imperfect strips an additional two-point symmetric failure mode may arise. The co-ordinates of these failure points are not constant - depending on the magnitude of the initial imperfection the symmetric point nearest the origin of co-ordinates lies in the approximate range: $0.06 < x/a < 0.31$.

The results shown in Figs. 2 and 3 clearly indicate that initial imperfections cause significant increases in the initial failure loads especially when the imperfections are moderately large, i.e. greater than the strip thickness. From the design standpoint this has important implications, since by "designing-in" imperfections enhanced strength may be realised.

Associated, additional strip centre-line deflections have also been plotted against the initial imperfection amplitude and these results are presented in Figs. 4 and 5 for CFRP and GFRP strips respectively. Fig. 4(a) shows that the associated strip centre deflections decrease rapidly and mildly nonlinearly as the imperfection amplitude increases. For positive z-direction loading the difference between the associated deflections for uncoupled and two-layer strips does not change much as the imperfection amplitude increases, whereas there is a significant reduction in this difference when the loading direction is reversed. It is interesting to note also that despite the positive z-direction initial failure loads exceeding the negative values throughout the range of imperfection amplitudes (see Fig. 2(a)) the in-

Fig. 4(a) Associated additional strip centre-line deflection versus imperfection amplitude for a simply supported CFRP strip.

Fig. 4(b) Associated additional strip centre-line deflection versus imperfection amplitude for a clamped CFRP strip.

Fig. 5(a) Associated additional strip centre-line deflection versus imperfection amplitude for a simply supported GFRP strip.

Fig. 5(b) Associated additional strip centre-line deflection versus imperfection amplitude for a clamped GFRP strip.

verse situation applies in respect of the associated strip centre deflections (compare the full-line curves (a) and (b) on Fig. 4(a)).

Fig. 4(b) shows the associated strip centre-line deflection - imperfection amplitude relationship for clamped CFRP strips. One point of interest concerning these results is that the two-layer, associated strip centre-line deflection for positive loading and zero initial imperfection amplitude significantly exceeds that of the uncoupled strip loaded negatively even though the initial failure load for the former strip is approximately 25% lower than that of the latter (see Fig. 2(b)).

The remaining set of results, i.e. the associated strip centre-line deflections for GFRP simply supported and clamped strips are shown in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) respectively. These results show broadly similar trends to those for CFRP strips and therefore do not merit further discussion here. Nevertheless, they constitute potentially useful design information and, therefore, they have been included for this reason as well as for the sake of completeness.

CONCLUSIONS

A study of the effects of imperfection amplitude and lay-up antisymmetry on the initial flexural failure response of uniformly loaded, clamped and simply supported, GFRP and CFRP strips has been described. The quantities of primary design interest, i.e. the initial failure loads and the associated strip centre-line deflections, have been presented in dimensionless graphical form to facilitate their widest application. The initial failure loads etc. exhibit a number of features, which are summarised below:

- (1) The initial failure loads are direction dependent, i.e. clamped strips are generally stronger when loaded in the positive z-direction and simply supported strips are stronger when loaded in the opposite direction.
- (2) The initial failure loads increase as the amplitude of the initial imperfection increases, and also as the number of constituent laminae increases.
- (3) In flat strips failure initiates in the strip surface either at the strip centre, or at the strip edges. However, in imperfect strips a second, two-point symmetric failure mode of variable location may arise.
- (4) The associated strip centre-line deflections decrease as the initial imperfection increases, but increase as the number of laminae increases.
- (5) The initial failure loads may be significantly enhanced by utilising "designed-in" imperfections.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to record his indebtedness to the Department of Engineering for providing computing facilities and also to his father, Mr. George Turvey, for his skill and care exercised in the preparation of the figures.

NOTATION

- a : Strip width.
- A_{11} , A_{12} : Extensional stiffnesses.
- B_{11} : Coupling stiffness.
- D_{11} , D_{12} : Flexural stiffnesses.
- $D_T (= \lambda h^3 / 12)$: Reference flexural stiffness.

- ϵ_x : Strip mid-plane strain.
 E_L, E_T : Longitudinal and transverse elastic moduli.
 h : Strip thickness.
 κ_x : Strip curvature.
 M_x : Stress couple.
 N_L : Number of laminae in the strip/laminate.
 N_x : Stress resultant.
 q : Lateral pressure.
 $\bar{q} (= qa^2 s_T^{-1} h^{-2})$: Dimensionless initial failure load.
 s_1, s_2, s_{12} : Lamina stresses (longitudinal, transverse and shear).
 s_L, s_T, s_{LT} : Failure strengths (longitudinal, transverse and shear).
 t_i, t_j : Thicknesses of the i^{th} and j^{th} laminae.
 u : Displacement in the x -direction.
 $w(w^0, w_1)$: Deflection (initial, additional).
 w_0 : Strip centre initial deflection/imperfection.
 $\bar{w} (= w D_T s_T^{-1} a^{-2} h^{-2})$: Dimensionless deflection.
 $\bar{w}_1 (|\bar{w}_1|_c)$: Dimensionless additional deflection (absolute value at the strip centre).
 x, y, z : Cartesian co-ordinates.
 ν_{LT}, ν_{TL} : Poisson's ratios.
 $()'$: Total derivative with respect to x .

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